

DISTRIBUTION CHARACTERISTICS OF CHICKEN ECTOPARASITES

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Abstract. This article presents literature data and results of preliminary research about ectoparasites that are widespread and cause great economic damage in chicken coops and some poultry farms. Their biology, distribution, clinical signs, epizootology and preventive measures are presented.

Key words: arachnology, mite, arthropods, arachnoidea, arthropoda, parasitiformes, argas persicus, *Argas persicus*, Mallophagosis, Dermanissiosis, larva, nymph, imago, Ixodid, parasite, bloodsucker, bed bug, straw

Enter. Work was carried out at the government level to develop measures to further improve the system of state support for the poultry industry. On June 15, 2022, the president's decision PQ-281 was signed, in which comprehensive support for the poultry industry in our Republic was signed. support and development, increase the volume of production of competitive products, establish mechanisms for stable supply of poultry farms' demand for feed in order to direct poultry products to domestic and foreign markets, attract large segments of the population to the sector It is aimed to increase legal culture, as well as organize scientific and technical approaches and effective use of information technology in the network.

Taking into account the tasks assigned to specialists in the field, it was found that various ectoparasites of poultry hinder the rapid development of this industry. One group of these ectoparasites are mites that parasitize poultry, and in recent years, when the epizootological situation in poultry farms was studied in our republic, scientific research works on ectoparasites of chickens and the diseases caused by them were almost not conducted.

Relevance of the topic. *Argas persicus*, Mallophage, *Dermanissus gallinarum* ectoparasites that call arachnids in poultry are common among chickens and other poultry species. We mainly refer to *Argas persicus* species, according to systematics: Arthropoda phylum, Arachnoidea class, Parasitiformes family, Ixodoidea large family, Argasidae family, *Argas persicus* species is a bird mite.

When these mites attack the bird's body, an allergic reaction causes itchiness and stress, and the birds begin to scratch the soft part of the soil with their claws. This lowers the productivity of poultry. The study of this topic in poultry farms is of great importance for

practice and consists in studying the species composition of ectoparasites and their harmful effects on poultry in the care of the population, private auxiliary farms and farms, and improving measures to combat them.

Research materials and methods. Our research was carried out on chickens kept in public henhouses in Payariq district, Samarkand region, and in the chicken house of the "Mega Project" vivarium of the Samarkand State Veterinary Medicine, Animal Husbandry and Biotechnology University. 15-25 chickens were selected from chicken houses in each house to diagnose chickens with ectoparasites. Collection of ectoparasites was carried out according to the generally accepted method. The chicken was previously treated with talc containing one of the preparations from the group of artificial peritroites (neostomazan), which caused temporary paralysis of the arthropods. The collection of ectoparasites from chickens was done by scratching on white paper, and then they were collected in test tubes containing 70% ethyl alcohol. Material was collected to determine the number of red ticks in chickens: bedding, straw, rags, debris in cracks. A special scalpel wrapped with cotton dipped in glycerin was used to collect material from the small slits of poultry cages. Calculation of the number of ectoparasites (m^2) and identification of species was carried out in the laboratory using determinants.

Research results and their analysis. During the period of June, July, August, September and October of 2023, 5 poultry farms were inspected in Payariq district, as a result, 184 copies of insects and poultry lice were found, including 89 copies of cockroaches and 95 copies of chicken mites were detected. All sex and age groups of birds were examined in the following order: head circumference, abdomen and cloaca circumference were organoleptically examined. Collection work was carried out mainly in the evening, when all the birds were asleep. In total, 378 m^2 of poultry houses were inspected and 368 copies of mites were sampled. The average number of mallophage, *Dermanissus gallinarum*, was 15/ m^2 . In all farms, 197 chickens were examined by scratching, and 88% of them were found to be infected with ectoparasites of *Argas persicus*, Mallofag, and *Dermanissus gallinarum* species.

Analysis of the distribution of ectoparasites in poultry houses showed that they were detected in all farms (100%). The fauna of ticks includes 1 species, the fauna of carnivores includes 2 species. Wide spread of these ectoparasites is associated with low sanitary standards of poultry houses, lack of timely and regular treatment of chickens with insecticides and acaricides in poultry houses.

USED LITERATURES:

1. Э.Х.Эргашев, Ж.Ш.Шопулатов Хайвонларнинг арахно-энтомоэларии билан протозоозларии. (65-73 бетлар) “Ўзбекистон” нашриёти 1973 й.
2. Dj.Azimov, A.I.yatusevich, X.B.Yunusov, R.B.Davlatov, B.T.Norqobilov, SH.A.Djabbarov, A.S.Daminov, A.O.Oripov, A.G'.G'afurov, N.E.Yuldashov, SH.X.Qurbanov. Parazitologiya va invasion kasalliklar. Darslik. Toshkent “Fan ziyosi” 2024.
3. Jabborov, G., & Rayimqulov, I. X. (2022). QO ‘Y VA ECHKILARNING EKTOPARAZITLARI VA ULARGA QARSHI DORI VOSITALARINI SINOVDAN O‘TKAZISH. *AGROBIOTEKNOLOGIYA VA VETERINARIYA TIBBIYOTI ILMIY JURNALI*, 86-89.
4. Eshkoraev, A. M., Raimkulov, I. K., Tursunkulov, A. R., & Rasulov, R. A. (2024). PREVENTION OF DICTIOCAULOSIS IN CATTLE (literature review). *World scientific research journal*, 25(1), 35-39.
5. Хушназаров, А. Х., Райимкулов, И. Х., Эшқораев, А. М., & Давлатов, Р. Б. (2023). Қуён эймериозининг кимёпрофилактикаси. *SCHOLAR*, 1(2), 56-62.
6. Iskandar Haydarovich Rayimqulov, Ravshan Berdiyevich Davlatov, Xudoynazar Beknazarovich Yunusov. Parrandalarni ektoparazitlardan asraylik. “Veterinariya meditsinasi” 4-son maxsus “AGROZOOVETSERVIS” Co., Ltd. 2023.12.24 (50-51).
7. Хушназаров, А., Райимкулов, И., & Эшқораев, А. (2023). ЗАМОНАВИЙ КАТАКЛАРДА ҚУЁНЛАРНИ БОҚИШ УСУЛЛАРИ. *Евразийский журнал медицинских и естественных наук*, 3(1 Part 2), 52-57.

8. Khushnazarov, A., Rayimkulov, I., & Eshkoraev, A. (2023). METHODS OF KEEPING RABBITS IN MODERN CAGES. *Eurasian Journal of Medical and Natural Sciences*, 3(1 Part 2), 52-57.
9. Khushnazarov, A. H., Rayimkulov, I. H., Eshkoraev, A. M., & Davlatov, R. B. (2023). CHEMIOPROPHYLAXIS OF EMERIOZINING IN RABBIT. *SCHOLAR*, 1(2), 56-62.
10. Раимкулов, И., Хушназаров, А., & Эшкораев, А. (2023). Способы кормления кроликов в современных клетках. *in Library*, 1(1), 52-57.
11. Раимкулов, И., Хушназаров, А., Эшкораев, А., & Давлатов, Р. (2023). Химиофилактика эмериоза кроликов. *in Library*, 1(1), 56-62.
12. Rayimkulov, I. X., & Khushnazarova, M. I. (2023). SCIENTIFIC BASIS OF FIGHT AGAINST PARASITIC DISEASES OF AGRICULTURAL ANIMALS.
13. Rayimkulov, I. X., & Xushnazarova, M. I. (2023). QISHLOQ XO 'JALIK HAYVONLARINING PARAZITAR KASALLIKLARGA QARSHI KURASHISHNING ILMIY ASOSLARI.
14. Khatamov, A. K., & Salimov, H. S. Results of a Study to Determine the Lethal Doses (Ld100 and Ld50) of *S. Typhimurium* in Experiments on Laying Chickens. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 4(1), 164-168.
15. Давлатов, Р. Б., Насимов, Ш. Н., Ниёзов, Х. Б., Жабборов, Ш. А., Хўджамшукуров, Ш. А., & Сафаров, Х. А. (2019). Парранда касалликларини профилактикаси ва даволаш бўйича ТАВСИЯЛАР. *Тошкент-2019*, 21-26.
16. Давлатов, Р. Б., Салимов, Х. С., & Худжамшукуров, А. Н. (2018). Парранда касалликлари" ўқув қўлланма Самарқанд.
17. Давлатов, Р. Б., Салимов, Х. С., & Тоиров, Ж. Э. (2019). ЧУВСТВИТЕЛЬНОСТЬ КОЛИБАКТЕРИОЗА ПТИЦ К АНТИБИОТИКАМ. In *СОВРЕМЕННОЕ СОСТОЯНИЕ, ТРАДИЦИИ И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ В РАЗВИТИИ АПК* (pp. 39-44).
18. Газнакулов, Т. К., Орипов, А. О., Сафаров, А. А., Хушназаров, А. Х., Давлатов, Р. Б., Абдухакимов, Ш., & Мавланов, С. (2023). ХС Салимов, МК Бутаев, ЗЭ Рузиев,—Биохафсизлик.
19. Давлатов, Р. Б., Салимов, Х. С., & Хўджамшукуров, А. Н. (2018). Паррандалар касалликлари. *Ўқув қўлланма, Самарқанд-2018*, 10.
20. Давлатов, Р. Б., Салимов, Х. С., & Тоиров, Ж. Э. (2018). ВОПРОСЫ ЭПИЗООТОЛОГИИ ЭШЕРИХИОЗА ПТИЦ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ. In *Современное состояние, традиции и инновационные технологии в развитии АПК* (pp. 67-73).
21. Ниязов, Ф. А., Давлатов, Р. Б., & Дурдиев, Ш. К. (2007). Особенности ассоциированного течения эмериоза и колибактериоза птиц. In *Болезни птиц в промышленном птицеводстве. Современное состояние проблемы и стратегия борьбы. Матер. научно-произв. конф* (pp. 324-327).
22. Butaeva, I. M., Salimov, H. S., & Davlatov, R. B. (2020). On The Diagnosis Of Mixed Bacterial Infections Of Birds. *International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology*, 29(9s), 2308-2315.
23. Salimov, H. S., & Kambarov, A. A. (2016). Epizootology, textbook.
24. Salimov, X. S., Qambarov, A. A., & Salimov, I. X. Epizootologiya va infeksiyon kasalliklar" darslik 2021 yil. *F. Nasimov nashriyoti*.
25. Эшкораев, А., Хушназаров, А., & Давлатов, Р. (2023). Развитие, эпизоотология, лечение и профилактика эмериоза кроликов. *in Library*, 1(1), 65-71.
26. Ergashov, S. I., Xushnazarov, A. X., & Davlatov, R. B. (2023). QUYONLAR EYMERIOZNI DAVOLASHDA KENG QO 'LLANILADIGAN PREPARATLAR. *Journal of new century innovations*, 22(3), 58-64.